

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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Florida's West Coast *Karenia brevis* bloom – Spring 2023

Fig. 1. Mapped *Karenia brevis* cell concentrations 26 days apart in March 2023. Note the offshore stations on 28 March to 4 April 2023 (gray circles right panel) have no *K. brevis* cells in surface samples. <https://floridadep.gov/algalbloom>

On the morning of 6 March 2023, the National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science (NOAA) issued an alert warning of “moderate to high risk of respiratory irritation” due to a *Karenia brevis* bloom along the southwest coast of Florida. This was no surprise to the many beachgoers who walk Florida’s shorelines every day and frequently see dead fish washed up on the beaches during harmful algal blooms (HABs). The city or municipal government of the small towns along the west Florida coast routinely budget for beach clean ups during the nearly annual harmful algal blooms. But dead fish are especially problematic during peak holiday seasons or, in this case, spring break week(s) when schools recess and many visitors flock to Florida’s wide, warm beaches. The “halo” effect of HABs can cause significant losses in revenue as the news, often exaggerated, is broadcast.

In an interview with the Washington Post (reported by A. Ajasa) Dr. Rick Stumpf (NOAA) noted that *K. brevis* cells often accumulate inshore in late summer and are pushed offshore to the mid shelf area of Florida’s west coast) by winter winds associated with high-pressure systems [1,2] the persistent northerly winds do not occur

K. brevis cells remain inshore. Stumpf speculates this is what happened in March 2023. It should be noted that while *K. brevis* blooms are known to occur at all seasons of the year, there are times when they are more frequent. High inshore cell concentrations are affected by wind patterns of frontal systems, hydrographic conditions like upwelling and in turn, nutrients upwelled to the surface waters [3]. Stumpf added “If you have a year where we don’t get those persistent northerly winds pushing it out it [HABs] can hang around. And that’s what’s happening this year.”

Florida’s coast lines are some of the most closely observed marine areas. A number of State, Federal and non-governmental organizations and university programs contribute their resources to help forewarn citizens, public health officials, resource managers, property owners and tourists of conditions that are conducive to HABs (see below). These agencies also have willing volunteers who serve as citizen scientists and help crowd source data along vast stretches of the 1,062 km west Florida coastline. The most recent reports of the spring 2023 *K. brevis* blooms show a decline in the cell concentrations nearshore and no reports of surface

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concentrations offshore (Fig. 1). Perhaps 2023 summer vacation plans can go to plan after all.

As I reviewed the various sources of information on *K. brevis* cell concentrations, respiratory safety, bloom status, environmental information relevant to transport and landfall that are now publicly available to researchers, resource managers and the public alike, I am amazed at the technology. My thoughts go back to early November 1st, a Sunday morning in 1987. There were thousands of large, leaf-like dinoflagellates tumbling around in a Petri dish on the microscope stage. We did not know much about *K. brevis* in North Carolina before 1987. There had never been a red tide along our coast. But radio reports of coughing and sneezing by dogs and their owners at the beach caused me to learn, and quickly, about what was happening. I had never seen these dinoflagellate cells before and tentatively identified them from a photo in the *Memoirs of the Hourglass Cruises* [4]. Without being an expert taxonomist, one can tentatively identify *Karenia (brevis)* species and understand the potential consequences of having six million cells l⁻¹ in the first samples. Later we learned there were no records of this species anywhere on the US east coast except for a few samples from below Jacksonville FL.

There was an urgency beyond being able to deal with questions from the public about what was happening on the beaches. Recreational shellfish had opened mid-October and the commercial shellfishing season was scheduled to start the next day, 2 November. My first call was to P. Fowler, a friend and colleague who worked with North Carolina Shellfish Sanitation. When I explained the situation to her, she looked for any information in her files on Florida Red Tides and joined me at the Beaufort NC NOAA lab. Time was passing quickly and we knew if notices to cancel commercial shellfishing were going to be signed and posted in time to be effective the next day, we needed to contact the laboratory directors immediately.....yes, on Sunday. Fowler called Dr. William Hogarth, Director of the NC Division of Marine Fisheries and Dr. Ford Cross, Director of the NOAA facility was advised. They must have been alarmed by the concern in our voices

Fig. 2. A HAB event known as the *North Carolina Red Tide* occurred on November 1, 1987. Toxic *Karenia brevis* cells traveled from Florida via the Gulf Stream into the colder coastal waters near Cape Lookout, North Carolina. This resulted in a loss of ~\$25 million (~\$64 million in 2022 dollars).

because they joined us within 30 minutes to be updated on the findings. Notices to close commercial shellfishing were posted along the central NC coasts during the late afternoon of Sunday, 2 November. No toxic shellfish reached the market. Forty-eight recreational shellfishers were not so fortunate. They met the case definition for neurotoxic shellfish poisoning but their illnesses were generally mild and quickly resolved [5].

Monday morning, November 2nd Dr. Karen Steidinger tentatively verified our taxonomy and after the live samples arrived in Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission Lab in St. Petersburg FL, Tuesday, there was no longer a question. The North Carolina coast was fully involved in a massive *K. brevis* bloom that kept some of the state's 1,480 km² shellfish harvesting areas closed in until early May 1988. In trying to answer questions about where the cells had come from and how long the bloom would remain, we had strong support from Dr. Steidinger and her staff. But these were truly uncharted waters and *Karenia* proved to be more resilient and temperature tolerant than anyone suspected. Certainly, remotely sensed imagery would have been helpful, but NASA's Ocean Zone Color Scanner on Nimbus 7 launched in 1976 was not operational after 1986. Thermal imagery from the National Weather Service was not available but Dr. Steven Baig from the Coral Gables facility was able to provide a product he used for estimating the location and speed of the western wall of the Gulf Stream in the

US South Atlantic Bight. This would be important for understanding the transport of cells from a bloom off Naples FL (24 August 1987) via the Florida Current and the Gulf Stream to NC by mid-October [6].

Soon our requests for imagery, even thermal imagery, reached Dr. Rick Stumpf's (NOAA) office and he was able to provide thermal imagery that showed the intrusion of the Gulf Stream into Raleigh Bay on 19 October. This warm filament continued to move shoreward and by 22 October was within 7 km of the shore east of Cape Lookout NC. This parcel of water remained intact for at least 17 days and inshore waters of both Onslow and Raleigh Bays warmed from less than 20°C to 22-24°C in about six days. This warm, high salinity water mass served as a chemostat for transported *K. brevis* cells that moved down shore (south) from Raleigh Bay to Onslow Bay around Cape Hatteras NC in the coastal counter current into rich shellfishing areas (Fig. 2).

It seems easy as I write this now, but it took months and the efforts of many to put the parts of this transport event and subsequent HAB bloom together. However, the magnitude of this event served as the genesis of NOAA's Coast Watch program that provides open access satellite data at both regional and global scales as well as operational forecasts for harmful algal blooms.

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Minding the microbes: human pathogens and cyanobacterial blooms

Fig. 1. Cultures of isolated bacterial colonies in blood agar

Although cyanobacteria are well known for their capacity to produce a wide range of toxins, little is known about the potential health effects from exposure to other biotic components of cyanobacterial blooms. Often, when people participate in recreational activities and/or live near to areas which experience cyanobacterial blooms, they may complain of non-specific health symptoms such as headaches, nausea and stomach issues [1]. However, with many of these symptoms, they are unable to be ascribed to the known actions of the many toxins and bioactive compounds produced by cyanobacteria. Consequently, it is possible that other, uncharacterised constituents of the bloom may be contributing to these observed adverse health effects. Furthermore, such constituents could also be present alongside the known toxins produced by cyanobacteria.

During toxin assessment of a cyanobacterial bloom in Florida in 2018, a pilot study was carried out to examine the presence of possible human bacterial pathogens associated with the bloom. Samples were removed aseptically and transported back to the lab on ice. Sterile subsamples of the bloom material were plated onto Blood Agar and incubated at 35°C. Serial culturing was performed to produce pure cultures of isolated bacterial colonies (Figure 1). Samples from 2 isolated colonies then underwent biochemical tests and identification using a Biomerieux Vitek2 Compact microbial identification system. The remaining bloom material was freeze-dried and underwent extraction and analy-

sis of microcystins, anatoxin-a, cylindrospermopsin, guanitoxin and BMAA and isomers [2].

Microscopy showed *Microcystis aeruginosa* as the principal cyanobacterium present in the bloom material (Figure 2). Toxin analysis showed the presence of microcystin-LR according to UPLC-PDA and UPLC-MS at 4.6 mg/l. Co-occurring with this cyanotoxin was β -N-methylamino-L-alanine (BMAA) at 51 ng/l and a trace amount of guanitoxin according to LC-MS/MS and enzyme inhibition assay, respectively. Biochemical tests for the two isolated chemoheterotrophic bacteria showed them to be oxidase and catalase positive and negative for lactose fermentation, with one a Gram negative rod and the other a Gram negative rod with flagella. Assessment of the bacteria by the Vitek 2 identification system identified them as *Aeromonas sobria* and *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* with 93% and 98% probability, respectively.

Aeromonas sobria and *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* are known opportunistic pathogens and are ubiquitous in natural environments, including water [3,4]. Exposure to such bacteria is of particular concern for people with immunodeficiencies and underlying health conditions with *Aeromonas* having been shown to cause gastroenteritis and wound infections [5] and *Sphingomonas* often being associated with nosocomial infections due to contaminated water, solutions or instruments [6].

The presence of chemoheterotrophs and their potential influence on the toxic-

Fig. 2. Micrograph of *Microcystis aeruginosa*, dominant cyanobacterium in the bloom.

ity of blooms has been inferred for some time. Often when people are exposed to cyanobacteria, generic symptoms are often reported such as headaches, sore throat, vomiting and stomach pains, as highlighted by army cadets performing kayak exercises in *Microcystis* scums on a freshwater reservoir [7]. Furthermore, based on the current knowledge of *Aeromonas* and *Sphingomonas*, these bacteria are capable of causing such symptoms [8,9]. Other recorded chemoheterotrophic bacteria connected with cyanobacterial blooms include *Vibrio cholerae* and associated outbreaks of cholera coinciding with microcystin-containing cyanobacterial blooms in Bangladesh [10]. Consequently, such chemoheterotrophic bacteria have the potential to drastically affect the adverse health effects possible from exposure to such blooms.

The chemoheterotrophic bacteria isolated and identified here could be responsible for the symptoms observed by the people of Florida in 2018 although the bloom material will likely contain many more bacterial species and genera than those that were culturable. A greater understanding of the contribution by and health risk from chemoheterotrophic bacteria in cyanobacterial blooms is required.

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Blooms of a red tide species *Tripos furca* in the aquaculture area of the Penang Strait, Malaysia

Fig. 1. Photomicrograph of *Tripos furca* from Aman Island

Fig. 2. Map of Peninsular Malaysia showing the location of Aman Island, Penang (A) and the sampling stations (B).

Blooms of the red-tide-forming dinophyte *Tripos furca* (Fig. 1) were observed along Aman Island in the Penang Strait in May 2022 (Fig. 2). The species caused dense red discolorations in the coastal water (Fig. 3). Bloom events of the species also lead to low concentrations of dissolved oxygen in the water, which promote massive fish kills due to either hypoxia/anoxia or damage to fish gills [1]. Blooms in the Penang Strait, fortunately, did not cause fish kills in the aquaculture area of Aman Island, as early warning notices had been issued and the local farmers had taken further action by harvesting before the blooms approached the farms.

Fig. 3. Red tide phenomenon in Aman Island.

Monthly field sampling conducted in the area showed that the blooms were recorded from May to August 2022 (Fig. 4). A previous study in 2012 reported the occurrence of the species in Aman Island, with the cell density reaching 76,500 cells L⁻¹ [2]. In our study, the *Tripos furca* cell maximum of 1.2×10^6 cells L⁻¹ was detected in June 28th 2022 (Fig. 4). Blooms were associated with water temperatures of 30.5–32.0°C, which describes their occurrence during the dry season. Blooms of this species have also been observed in salinity ranges of 26.5–30.5, while pH range was 7.5 - 8.5. Low dissolved oxygen levels were also detected in the surface water column, 4–7 mg L⁻¹.

Fig. 4. Cell density of *Tripos furca* (cells L⁻¹) between May and August 2022 in Aman Island.

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A bloom of *Pyrodinium bahamense* in the port operations of a seafood processing plant, SE Gulf of Mexico

Fig. 1. Study area and sampling sites (S1-S6) in coastal waters of Campeche, Gulf of Mexico

The Mexican state agency CONAPESCA (National Aquaculture and Fisheries Commission) ranked the State of Campeche as seventh in the country in terms of fish catch volume with an active fleet of 3,401 artisanal fishing river boats and 26 plants along the coast providing processing capacity for fishing products. Most of the plants are adjacent to the landing areas, and the processed water is generally discharged directly into the sea without prior treatment. It should be noted that the wastewater discharge process is regulated by Mexican law. In 2005, the state agency for the protection of sanitary risks reported a bloom of a planktonic non-toxic dinoflagellate, *Blixaea quinquecornis*, in a sheltered port in the City of Campeche resulting in the discoloration of water.

As part of the monitoring program of harmful phytoplankton in areas with anthropogenic activities along the central coast of Campeche, six sites (depths of ca. 1 m) at three coastal localities (City of Campeche, Seybaplaya and Champotón; 19°17'52.55"-19°51'50.87"N, 90°30'47.37"-90°46'6.83"W) were sampled (Fig. 1). Sampling stations were chosen at the points of rainwater discharge or near the sites with anthropogenic impact and were monitored monthly from November 2021 to November 2022. Quantification of *P. bahamense* cells was performed according to the Utermöhl technique [1] The dinoflagellate *Pyrodinium bahamense* reached a maximum value of 1.2×10^6

cells L^{-1} in May 2022 at station S5 (Fig. 2), corresponding to port operations of a seafood processing plant. Salinity was 29.3, temperature 33.1°C, pH 7.9 and dissolved oxygen 9.1 $mg L^{-1}$. Discoloration of water was not observed.

Toxicity of *P. bahamense* in the subtropical waters

of the West Atlantic was recorded in the coastal zone of East Florida [2], and there is recent evidence for toxic populations of *P. bahamense* in the coastal waters of Campeche, coupled with the presence of paralytic shellfish toxins in fish collected off the coast of Campeche [3]. Along the Campeche coast, *P. bahamense* is widely distributed, with marked occurrences in the dry (February to May) and rainy (June to September) seasons in 2005, 2008, 2010, 2019 and with abundances ranging from 3.0×10^3 to 3.3×10^5 cells L^{-1} [4]. It should be considered one of the key species with the potential for forming blooms in the study area. The high abundances of *P. bahamense* along this coast may be indicative of eutrophication due to fluc-

Fig. 2. Net haul of blooming *Pyrodinium bahamense* in the port operations area of a seafood processing plant, SE Gulf of Mexico, with abundant detritus characteristic of a coastal shallow zone

tuations in environmental conditions caused by the intensity and type of human activities [5]. Near the northern coast of Yucatan Peninsula, from 2002-2011, the species was characteristic of the marinas of Telchac, Dzilám de Bravo and of the coast off Progreso, especially in the rainy season (F. del C. Merino-Virgilio, pers. comm.). The proximity of mangroves seems to favour the proliferation of the species. Therefore, it is essential to keep a record of bloom-forming planktonic species, with a special emphasis on harmful species that co-occur with production activities in coastal areas.

Acknowledgements

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The Sixteenth Session of the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB-XVI)

The 16th session of the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB-XVI) was held at FAO Headquarters 27-29 March 2023. The Panel reviewed the actions completed during the intersessional period, noted the progress made and that several of the UN Ocean Decade challenges are being addressed. The Panel concluded that the Decisions and Recommendations of the Fifteenth session (March 2021) had been implemented highly satisfactorily within the available resources. The major achievements reported, some still in progress, include: (i) the results from the ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics and ICES-IOC-IMO Working Group on Ballast and other Ship Vectors; (ii) the updates on the continued publication of the IOC Harmful Algae News; (iii) the implementation of three international training courses and several regional and in-country courses; (iv) the continued development of the regional activities in Western Pacific (IOC/WESTPAC/HAB); and the Caribbean (IOC/IOCARIBE/ANCA), the engagement, but shortage of resources, for South America (IOC/IPHAB/FANSA) and North Africa (IOC/IPHAB/HANA); (v) the advances of the PICES HAB-Section; (vi) the publication of the GlobalHAB “Guidelines for the study of climate change effects on HABs”; (vii) the publication of a Technical Guidance Document for the Development of Early Warning Systems for Marine Harmful Algal Bloom Events to be published, as a joint publication of FAO, IOC-UNESCO and IAEA, as a FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper; (viii) the continued compilation of data at all levels for the IPHAB-IODE Harmful Algae Information System with HAEDAT and OBIS databases as providers of high quality information on HAB events, status and trends of HAB occurrence and assessment of climate change impacts, and a toxin database linked to the taxonomic reference list via WoRMS; (ix) the advances achieved

by the strategy for Ciguatera; (x) the developments under the joint IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB science programme such as the advanced modelling and automated in situ observations workshops (xi) the opportunities the UN Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development brings to IPHAB for transformative science solutions for sustainable development of the ocean regarding HABs and (xii) the development of activities and partnerships carried out by the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) to promote and foster research and training on HABs.

The Panel took eleven decisions and endorsed two recommendations for the consideration of the IOC Assembly at its thirty-second session and of the FAO Committee on Fisheries (COFI). The decisions concern: (i) Regional HAB Programme Development taking into account the difference of support for the various groups and networks depending on whether they are affiliated to a regional IOC subsidiary body or not; (ii) the continuation of the Task Team on the Early Detection, Warning and Forecasting of HAB Events; with new terms of reference; (iii) the continuation of the Task Team on the development of the Harmful Algal Information System and a periodic Global Harmful Algal

Bloom Status Report with new terms of reference; (iv) the continuation of the Task Team on a Global Ciguatera Strategy for Improved Research and Management with new terms of reference; (v) the continuation of the Task Team on Harmful Algae and Desalination of Seawater to formulate a proposal for a joint FAO WHO water safety risk assessment for drinking water coming from desalination plants; (vi) the continuation of the Task Team on Biotxin Monitoring, Management and Regulations with new terms of reference; (vii) the continuation of the Task Team on Algal Taxonomy with new terms of reference; (viii) the continuation of the Task Team on Fish Killing Microalgae and Ecosystem Effects with new terms of reference; (ix) establishment of a Task Team on HAB Communication; (x) IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB beyond 2025; and (xi) the development of HAB Solutions (HAB-S) an UN Ocean Decade Programme Proposal.

Dr Philipp Hess (France) was elected as Chair and Dr Maggie Broadwater (USA) was elected as Vice-Chair. The Recommendations to the IOC Assembly encompass (i) the planned intersessional activities into a workplan and budget for the IOC HAB Programme 2024–2025; and (ii) the continuation of IPHAB with unchanged terms of reference.

Philipp Hess, Chair IPHAB & Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC-HAB Programme Coordinator

ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics Meeting

The joint ICES - IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGHABD) is an important forum for ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Seas) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC-UNESCO) to review and discuss HAB events, and to provide annual advice and updates on the state of HABs in the North Atlantic area region. It also facilitates interaction between scientists working in diverse areas of HAB science and monitoring and provides a forum for the interchange of various approaches to HAB research. The group reports to both the ICES Science Committee (SCICOM) and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) -IOC UNESCO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB).

The group's annual meeting, in hybrid format, was held 20th – 23rd March at Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Napoli, Italy. The meeting was attended by delegates from USA, UK, Ireland, France, Spain, Portugal, Netherlands, Germany, Poland, Sweden, Norway, Belgium and Estonia and was opened by Marina Montresor and Adriana Zingone. Over four days, discussion and presentations covered a variety of re-

lated topics including progress on the 3rd and final year of the groups current Terms of Reference (ToR) for the 2020-2022 cycle, new and current project research studies, and three year national reports and new findings in relation to Harmful Algal Bloom events recorded during 2022 in the ICES Atlantic region. Time was dedicated to defining the working groups next set of ToRs for the forthcoming three year cycle.

In addition to the review and summary of the Working Groups activities from the current ToR cycle there were a number of presentations, including, 'Harmful Algae News update'; 'HAB Monitoring in the Gulf of Naples'; 'Marine phytoplankton monitoring by molecular approaches'; 'Update on Metabarcoding/eDNA in Nordic countries'; 'Update on eDNA EU projects (TREC, BioOcean5D, Obama-Nest) and ROME eDNA network'; 'Automated observations of harmful algal algae in the Baltic Sea and the Kattegat-Skagerrak using imaging flow cytometry'; 'Update on satellite ocean colour discrimination of HABs'; 'US National Harmful Algal Bloom Observation Network'; 'GES-4SEAS EU Project - Achieving Good Environmental Status For Maintaining Ecosystem Services By Assess-

ing Integrated Impacts Of Cumulative Pressures'; 'Update on Tetrodotoxins in Netherlands' and 'Toxic bloom of *Prymnesium parvum* in the Oder River in 2022'.

The meeting was closed by Professor Chris Bowler, President, Board of Directors - Anton Dohrn Zoological Station where the next annual meeting is scheduled for April 2024, to be hosted by IFREMER, Nantes, France. For the next 3-year cycle, the working group will be co-chaired by Lars Johan Naustvoll (Norway) and Dave Clarke (Ireland). WGHABD, together with the ICES working groups for Phytoplankton and Microbial Ecology, and Introduction and Transfer of Marine Organisms are convening a joint theme session at the forthcoming ICES Annual Science Conference in Bilbao, Spain from 11th – 14th September on 'Integration of molecular tools for biodiversity, risk assessment, ecosystem advice within a changing climate'.

Information on HAB event occurrence in the North East Atlantic margin area is reported annually by the Working Group members and is publicly available in the Harmful Algal Event database (HAEDAT <http://haedat.iode.org/>) and also through Harmful Algal Information System (HAIS <https://data.hais.ioc-unesco.org/>).

Dave Clarke, WGHABD Chair

Workshop on an Early Warning System (EWS) for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in Morocco

From December 5 - 8th, 2022 an IOC-UNESCO workshop on Early Warning Systems for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) was held in Casablanca, Morocco, hosted by the Institut National de la Recherche Halieutique (INRH). This workshop, funded through IOC-UNESCO by the Norwegian Cooperation and Development Agency (NORAD), was organized in the framework of the IOC-UNESCO project «*Detection and Early Warning Systems (EWS) adapted to Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs)*», in partnership with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). This project addresses HAB-related issues which impact seafood safety due to toxin contamination of shellfish, fish and crustaceans, and mass mortalities of marine organisms. Development of an early warning system (EWS) to help mitigate the impact of HABs is thus desirable to help protect against HAB impacts.

The workshop objectives were to identify stakeholder priorities and to train national experts on data management, imaging and predictive modelling to implement an EWS of HAB events in Morocco. Forty-five experts participated in this workshop (Fig. 1), which was attended by representatives of

government agencies and other stakeholders in the aquaculture and shellfish processing industries as well as INRH scientists of the Marine Environment Monitoring Network (RSMM) responsible for the monitoring of HABs and marine biotoxins, INRH data analysts and IOC representatives.

The first thematic area dealt with the assessment of stakeholder priorities and requirements, current capacities, pre-existing and present gaps in knowledge and data acquisition, as well as limiting factors and resources in the establishment of an EWS in Moroccan coastal waters. Additional discussions took place on logistic issues related to the fulfillment of requirements for the laboratories to get an accreditation according to the ISO/IEC 17025 standard. Special interest was expressed about obtaining validation on analytical methods for toxin analysis and quantitative analysis of phytoplankton. Lectures and scientific presentations were given on different topics related to the HAB monitoring programme and EWS.

The second thematic area focused on training in R programming and predictive modeling systems that could be implemented for operational use to forecast the onset and duration of HAB episodes in Morocco. Also, train-

ing on the standardization of data from monitoring programs (levels of marine biotoxins in shellfish and abundance of harmful phytoplankton species in seawater) was provided to review adopted phytoplankton thresholds and potential forecasting models.

In Morocco, the monitoring programme in shellfish production areas, developed under the terms of the National Institute of Fisheries Research, Morocco (Institut National de Recherche Halieutique, INRH) is carried out in six regional centres (Nador, Tanger, Casablanca, Agadir, Laayoune and Dakhla) in compliance with the provisions of the Moroccan Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Rural Development, Continental Waters and Forestry (MAPMDREF), order no. 1950-17 related to the sanitary classification of shellfish production areas [1]. The monitoring protocols meet national and international health requirements (in particular those implemented by the EU market). Monitoring for seafood safety is carried out using two complementary approaches: regular monitoring and alert monitoring.

Monitoring of the classified shellfish production areas is carried out to safeguard public health and environmental quality. This monitoring covers microbiological and chemical parameters (inorganic and organic contaminants), toxigenic phytoplankton and marine biotoxins, according to the established sampling plan. These areas are monitored to revise the sustainability of their

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Fig. 1. Participants in the IOC-UNESCO workshop on Early Warning System (EWS) for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in Morocco. Casablanca, Morocco, December 4 – 8th 2022

HAB session during the Sixth Xiamen Symposium on Marine Environmental Sciences

A scientific session “Harmful algal blooms under changing climate: mechanisms, monitoring, and mitigation for a sustainable, safe and healthy ocean” was held during the Sixth Xiamen Symposium on Marine Environmental Sciences at Xiamen University, Xiamen, China, from 9 - 12 January 2023.

A total of 40 papers were accepted for this HAB session with 16 oral presentations covering the dynamics of HABs in the Pacific region. Topics spanned from ecological, physiological, and molecular responses of HAB species to biotic and abiotic drivers. The presentations also covered aspects of HAB monitoring, forecasting, and early detection using novel tools and instrumentation. Oral papers were presented in three three-hour sessions.

The session began with an invited lecture by Dr Satoshi Nagai, Japan Fisheries Research and Education Institute who shared his five years of research in predicting phytoplankton composition in Mombetsu, Hokkaido using metabarcoding and Artificial Intelligence technology. He illustrated how next-generation sequencing data were obtained from his study to clarify the seasonal dynamics of selected harmful algal species. He concluded that while the outcome of this application is promising, there are challenges to address before HAB prediction become possible.

Other highlights from the HAB session included the following:

Dr Kieng Soon Hii, University of Malaya, Malaysia, shared his research findings on current knowledge on the transcriptomic features of the toxic and non-toxic *Azadinium* and its implication in Azaspiracid biosynthesis.

Dr Shuwen Zhang, South China Normal University, China, demonstrated that the toxin production of *Pseudo-nitzschia* was enhanced by co-culturing *Pseudo-nitzschia* with *Noctiluca*, thus elucidating the interspecific interactions and successional mechanisms of HAB species.

Dr Monaliza Mohd Din, University Malaya, Malaysia, reported prolonged algal blooms in the inner Johor Strait that caused the formation of a hypoxic-anoxic dead zone, leading to an ecological disaster in the area.

Dr Yunyan Deng, Institute of Oceanology, China, described the active and inactive genes in resting cysts using *Scrippsiella acuminata* as the model species. Her findings enhanced current understanding of the molecular processes in dinophyte resting cysts.

Dr Jianping Li, The University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, China, highlighted the recent advancement of optical technology in real-time plankton monitoring and sea trial of instruments that he has successfully deployed

and how to overcome biofouling in the highly eutrophic waters of Daya Bay. He also explained how machine learning was adopted to identify plankton species in the samples, and the result was comparable to those obtained from the microscopic enumeration.

Dr Anouk Olleveil, Flanders Marine Institute, Belgium, introduced a video plankton recorder (VPR) approach to investigate the plankton compositions in shallow and turbid waters in Belgian coastal waters (North Sea). She further clarified the usefulness of the VPR despite limitations in shallow coastal waters and the detection of small plankton species.

As well as the above highlighted presentations, other remarkable HAB research findings, from oral and poster presenters in this HAB session can be found at https://melmeeting.xmu.edu.cn/xmas/program_byday_poster.asp (E-Posters) and https://melmeeting.xmu.edu.cn/xmas/program_bysession.asp?id=7100075 (abstracts). This HAB session has shown the progress of HAB knowledge in the region and provided a platform to strengthen regional and international collaborations in addressing the expanding HAB issues worldwide.

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Continued from p. 8

classification and update it whenever necessary according to reported results and the regulatory provisions of decree 1950-17 from the Moroccan Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Freshwater and Rural Affairs (MAPMDREF) [1].

The potentially toxic microalgal species/genera identified in the framework of the Moroccan monitoring programme in shellfish production areas include: *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp, *Alexandrium* spp, *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Dinophysis* spp, *Protoceratium reticulatum*, *Gonyaulax spinifera*, *Lingulodinium polyedra*, *Prorocentrum* spp, *Karenia* spp, *Os-*

treopsis spp and *Coolia* spp. Monitoring of the three groups of regulated marine biotoxins (PSP, ASP and LSP) in shellfish products has enabled the detection of these toxins which in some cases exceeded the regulatory limits.

By the end of the workshop, participants expressed their satisfaction for the opportunity to exchange views on HAB management aiming to strengthen biotoxin protocols and alerts in Morocco. It was agreed that continuing to test a pilot EWS for HABs in Morocco is highly desirable, timely and relevant to everybody concerned.

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Red Tides Archives

In HAN 72 we introduce you to a new series of unedited contributions, rescued from red tide archives, which are relics from the days when the HAB community was starting to develop. The first is a transcription of an “After-dinner speech” by Tim Wyatt, HAN founding editor from 1992 to 2013, at the II International Conference on Toxic Dinoflagellate Blooms, Key Biscayne, Florida, 31 Oct - 5 Nov 1978.

“Let my people go” is a collection of extreme scenarios of high biomass events nowadays called Ecosystem Disruptive Algal Blooms (EDAB), combined with one of Tim’s favourite exercises: to find a scientific interpretation of anthropological and mythological issues.

Let My People Go¹

In classical times, the fringes of the Arabian and Red Seas were inhabited by the Ichthyophagoi or fish-eaters. Their descendants are the Shihuh and other tribes living along the coasts of Oman and Makran to this day. We learn from Strabo, from Diodorus Siculus, and from other ancient authors that these people lived exclusively on fish, that their camels too were fed on fish, and that their houses were built of the bones of fish (and whales) and roofed with the skins of camels. Diodorus tells us that these people disposed of their dead by laying them on the rocks and letting the tide take them. He commented that “by making their own interment a nutriment of the fish, they have a life which follows in singular fashion a continuous cycle throughout all eternity.” The same life style has been noted by mediaeval and modern travellers, so that eternity in this case has lasted at least 2000 years. Vito Volterra in Italy [2] (and independently Lotka [3] in America) put this model into mathematical form in the early part of our own century, and by so doing, started the modern game of ecological modelling. “The initial impulse for Volterra’s studies was provided by the sardines of the Adriatic, just as the inspiration for Diodorus’ remark was the sardines of the Ichthyophagoi. A recent view of the models which have developed as a result of these early stimuli states that they have the “neutral stability of the frictionless pendulum” (p

50 in [4]). Translated from the idiom of modern physics, this simply means that they cycle throughout all eternity, or at least until someone switches the computer off. Quite rightly, in an age which has become aware that there may be limits to growth, modern ecologists have become very interested in the notion of stability, whether it exists in nature, and if so, how it is achieved. To balance this concern, I should like tonight to talk about ecological instability. As people at this gathering are well aware, nature does not always seem to behave in a stable fashion, at least over short time scales. If we could throw some light on the mechanisms whereby instability is initiated, we might at the same time learn something of the ways in which ecosystems normally maintain themselves in that state which we recognise as stable. Epidemiologists and those concerned with pest control face analogous problems, and it is not surprising that their models paralleled those already mentioned. Ross’s studies of the epidemiology of malaria for example led to a model which is formally identical to Volterra’s, and in fact preceded it slightly in time. Let us then look at some ecosystems in which the stabilizing mechanisms, whatever they be, have temporarily ceased operation.

Some Case Histories

In recognition of the fact that our hosts are Americans, I begin with that small lake in Wisconsin, Lake Mendota, made

famous by the pioneering studies of Lindeman. Its story however begins about fifty years before Lindeman’s, in July 1884. That summer 200 to 300 tons of perch died and drifted ashore around the lake. In the subsequent weeks myriads of flies appeared in the neighbourhood, and Superintendent Buckmaster of the State Insane Hospital noted that the gardens of that institution contained unusually large numbers of dead swallows and sparrows. It was later suggested in a report to the US Fisheries Commission that the perch had been poisoned by some natural event in the lake, and that the toxin was then transmitted to the birds by the flies.

A more recent and dramatic event of this kind occurred in 1968 near the Farne Island’s which lie off the north-east coast of England. (The event is briefly referred to in Peter Ayres paper at this conference). Here a bloom of *Gonyaulax tamarensis* led to mortality of invertebrates and fish, and notably to the death of virtually all the shags nesting on the Farnes. Other fish-eating birds also died in large numbers, and there were 78 cases of PSP among the local human population.

Plagues of insects are an almost inevitable concomitant of any large accumulation of carrion. A very extensive mortality of fish following a red tide occurred in Walvis Bay in South West Africa in 1880, and was followed by flies. This is one of my favourite dead fish stories, and I take the liberty of quoting at length from the letter of Mr Koch in which this event was recorded. The letter was published by Gilchrist in 1914, and reads “On the evening of the 20th December 1880, some native fishermen procured eels, which were unknown. On the following morning these were again found, and other fish were seen, the natives, however, fearing to make use of them on account of the peculiar odour of the water. At nine o’clock of the same day, it being spring tide, Mrs Koch, along with the wife of Mr Bauman, the missionary, visited the beach and saw hundreds of living and struggling fish cast up on the sand by each wave and this continued for three more days. On Christmas’ Eve it was almost impossible to proceed to the church on account of the odour, and it was scarcely possible to walk about without stepping on the dead fish. The *Alfred Lewis* was in the

1) Note from the author. In 1978, ecological stability was a central issue. Robert May [1] had questioned that complexity begets stability, and argued that ecosystems become less stable as complexity increases. The plagues illustrate that ecosystems can sometimes become extremely unstable. These days the plagues of Exodus would likely be attributed to climate change, pollution, or even some obscure injustice. Then, the deliverables, milestones, stakeholders were more discrete. Life was less macdonaldized

Image from the Egyptian Book of the Dead (c. 1275 BC)

bay at the time, but the water was so blood red and smelt so badly that she left for Sandwich Harbour where fewer fish had been cast up. Everything of a white colour became black, even the deck houses of the *Alfred Lewis*. After a few months the skeletons on the shore in the neighbourhood of the lagoon formed a pile five to six feet in height. Then began a plague of flies. It was only possible to drink a cup of coffee by keeping the hand in constant movement and it was only in September that it became bearable." The Walvis Bay region is well known for its fish mortalities, as indeed is the entire coast of South West and southern Africa. I shall refer to two other African episodes shortly. Less well known are the subsequent deaths of flamingos, baboons, and perhaps eels which succeed them.

This leads me to my next story, which is African with American connections, and the opportunity to get in a plug for a forthcoming paper. Captain Benjamin Morrell, an American sealer, reported seeing not less than half a million "dead seals on Possession Island in 1828 with their skins still on them". He described a similar occurrence at seal colonies in Luderitz Bay, 17 miles farther north, whilst living colonies were seen at the Long Islands on the open coast between the two sites. Morrell's veracity has often been called into question, but there are some indications that in this instance he was telling the truth. If this should eventually prove to be so, then a toxic dinoflagellate bloom seems a likely candidate to account for the mortality. I have argued Morrell's case at some length in a paper which will appear in the near future [5].

The episodes I have mentioned so far are fairly commonplace, and most of you will have your own favorites in this genre. My next choice is more bizarre, and consequently less believable. The scene was Talara in northern Peru, January 1925, which then witnessed simultaneously a massive incursion of tropical water from the north - the famous El Niño current - and the first rains in 34 years. The combination was devastating, and since I cannot hope to emulate the fluid prose of Robert Cushman Murphy, I resort once more to quotation. The description is from his magnificent book on the Oceanic Birds of South America (1936, Vol. I, p 285). "Dead fish, mingled with untold numbers of birds, strewed the tide lines for hundreds of miles as the ocean turned sour, and thirty-five thousand tons of new guano were washed from the islands by falling water. The northern coves became choked with flotsam from engorged stream beds, and sea snakes, alligators, and strange lizards were cast upon unfamiliar strands. Mulletts came out of the ocean to swim about in the squares and roadways of the petroleum towns, and, when the rains began to diminish, mosquitoes, and the 'caballitos del diablo' or dragon flies which prey upon them, were engendered in such swarms as had never been known." Murphy's use of the word *caballitos* seems particularly apt in such apocalyptic circumstances. The mixture of species is reminiscent of the Abominations of Leviticus.

More fantastic still is a series of events which occurred in the Saint Lucia Estuary in Natal in 1969. They were recorded briefly by John Grindley in

1970 [6]. Drought, evaporation, and withdrawal of water for irrigation apparently combined to produce very high salinities in the estuary, which killed fish, invertebrates and vegetation. This was in March. In July and August, during calm spells following rain, there were two separate outbreaks of red water dominated by *Noctiluca*. In July a plague of Chironomidae occurred, of a species favoured by enriched bottom substrates. These in turn led to a plague of tinyphid spiders which prey on midges. These spiders are orb-web weavers which disperse aerially. Finally, "In the Lester Point area the spiders' webs became so dense that plants and branches of trees were completely smothered and killed." Grindley proposed that the chironomid plague was caused by the reduction of predatory control of the aquatic larvae consequent on the events in March. The *Noctiluca* bloom is not obviously connected to the other plagues, but may be linked to the unusual climatic circumstances.

The next chain reaction I have chosen to mention occurred in the years 1847 to 1851, and its repercussions are still being felt today. I refer to the "Great Hunger", the worst of the Irish potato famines. The proximate cause of the famine - if we ignore the social and political angles - was a fungus, *Phytophthora infestans*, which causes potato blight in the varieties then being planted. The sequelae to famine are too well known in our own time, and I do not need to spell out the ghastly details of suffering and pestilence. The population of Ireland in 1841 was between 8 and 9 million. Famine, typhus and dysentery probably killed at least a million, though precise numbers have never been established. Millions more fled the country - emigration is a euphemism for this exodus. By 1855, 3 million had gone, most of them to the United States. By 1891, following several less severe famines, the total population of Ireland was reduced to less than 3 million.

The Plagues of Egypt

Most of you are - I am sure - familiar with the plagues of Egypt described in Chapters 7 to 12 of Exodus, and as students of red tides will long ago have recognised that the first of these plagues

was a population explosion of some as yet unidentified algal species. I am not concerned here with the liturgical and dramatic aspects of the story, though these have of course ensured its survival. Why then should I be concerned with it at all? Many commentators have pointed out that all but the last of the plagues have parallels at other times, that they are in fact almost annual afflictions of Egypt, and that to pursue the matter further is a vanity. It is true enough that the Nile may appear red when the flood waters of Abyssinia bring down their mud, that great numbers of frogs and flies occur in some years when the river rises, and that locusts are a constant threat to crops in these arid regions. It is true too that the *khamsin*, the blistering wind, can carry dust and sand from the desert sufficient to obscure the sun. But it is easier for me personally to believe that the events recorded in *Exodus* were extraordinary, and that ordinary events of these kinds should become central to one of the great faiths of the world.

In ancient Egyptian belief, the Nile was formed by the tears of Isis, weeping for her husband Osiris who was slain by his brother Set. By means of Isis' tears "the country is converted into a sea, and nothing appears but the cities, which look like islands in the Aegean. At this season boats no longer keep to the course of the river, but sail right across the plain." This passage is taken from Herodotus, but would equally describe Egypt right up until the end of the nineteenth century. The Nile begins to rise in July and the flood is at its height in August and September. As it recedes, enormous shallow lagoons are left behind in the delta region. Cut off from the declining river, and, if connected with the sea, only weakly flushed by the small tides of the eastern Mediterranean, these lagoons form suitable environments for intense algal blooms. It is not unreasonable to suppose that in one such lagoon, perhaps a very large one, in the Land of Goshen, that part of the eastern delta occupied by the Israelites in pharaonic times, an algal bloom turned into a red tide. Parts of the water-courses themselves might also, as semi-stagnant conditions set in, develop blooms. If the Nile flood had been less extensive than normal, hyper-salinification might have occurred. We have already seen some of

the scenarios which might follow such an event.

The Bible contains several versions of the plagues. The *Exodus* account has ten, which, in order, are (i) "and all the waters that were in the river were turned to blood"; (ii) "and the fish that was in the river died; and the river stank, and the Egyptians could not drink of the water of the river", "and the frogs came up, and covered the land of Egypt"; (iii) "and it became lice in man, and in beast; all the dust of the land became lice throughout all the land of Egypt." (according to my brother, who is a scholar of ancient languages including Old Testament Hebrew, the word here rendered as lice is probably gnats); (iv) "and there came a grievous swarm of flies and the land was corrupted by reason of the swarm of flies"; (v) "Behold, the hand of the Lord is upon thy cattle which is in the field, upon the horses, upon the asses, upon the camels, upon oxen, and upon the sheep: there shall be a very grievous murrain." Murrain is no specific disease of domestic animals; (vi) "a boil breaking forth with blains upon man, and upon beast". This despite the fact that murrain had already killed all the cattle! Blains are blisters or pustules; (vii) "and the Lord sent thunder and hail, and the fire ran along upon the ground; and the Lord rained hail upon the land of Egypt". This plague too killed animals and destroyed crops. Flax and barley were destroyed, but wheat and rye escaped; (viii) "and the locusts went up over all the land of Egypt and they did eat every herb of the land, and all the fruit of the trees which the hail had left"; (ix) "and there was a thick darkness in all the land of Egypt three days"; (x) "the Lord smote all the first-born in the land of Egypt." This too included the first-born (or simply chosen) of cattle.

Detailed examination of the text of *Exodus* has led to the belief that three different sources are combined here, no one of which mentions all ten plagues. These sources are labelled J, E and P, and the plagues of each are shown in the accompanying table. Further versions occur in Psalms 78 and 106. In my own reconstruction of the possible course of events, I have tried to account for all ten, since it is a relatively easy matter to delete some in order to comply with any one of the different versions. By this time, I am sure, you have

all guessed what is coming, that several case histories outlined earlier can be linked together in such a way that a plausible ecological model of the ten plagues preceding the *Exodus* emerges.

A red tide broke out in the eastern delta, exacerbated perhaps by unusual climatic conditions either locally or in the distant headwaters of the Blue Nile. This must have caused mortality among invertebrates and fish, or have accompanied such mortality as in the case of the Saint Lucia estuary. In either case, the water would soon have become de-oxygenated, beginning at the bottom. The surviving fish would rise to the surface and gasp for air, and eventually themselves die and be either cast ashore, or sink and further exacerbate the anoxia. Air-breathing aquatic insect larvae might of course survive, leading to plagues of mosquitoes, midges and other pests. "The death of the bulk of the fauna would have intensified the success of emergence, and would yield a source of carrion in which flies could breed. Frogs, since most of their oxygen requirements are met through the skin, would be forced from the water, and would seek cool shady places such as houses. There is little difficulty then in accounting for the first four plagues (blood, frogs, gnats and flies). Lake Mendota, Walvis Bay and Talara provide modern parallels. There is similarly little difficulty with regard to plagues 5 and 6 (murrain and boils). Biting insects attacking both people and their domestic stock would in excess numbers soon lead to extreme irritation. Scratching the wounds would then provide sores, blains, an attractive environment for the non-biting dipterans and other insects exploiting the dead fish and frogs, and for the pathogens they harbour (murrain, boils). The next two plagues, hail and locusts between them destroyed the crops. Locusts are a sufficiently common affliction that we need have no qualms about them. The same unusual climatic conditions which allowed the delta lagoons to develop red tide conditions, i.e. greater than average aridity, would cause dispersal of locusts in search of food. Hail on the other hand is rare in Egypt, and a storm sufficient to damage crops significantly would consume the entire annual precipitation allowance of several decades. Hail (frost, snow)

could however be simulated by the gossamer and webs of aerially dispersed spiders, and there is little doubt that these and other insect predators such as dragonflies would have responded to the super-abundance of prey provided by earlier plagues. Each insect plague would in turn “darken the sky” and give rise to the ninth plague.

The tenth plague, the death of first-born (or chosen) presumably must have occupied a period of several months or more. The poor innocent Egyptians (it was Jehovah who hardened the Pharaoh’s heart, not his own gods) were short of drinking water and food, and infected with all manner of pathogens borne by insects. They would have dispersed in search of help, and no doubt crowded into camps provided by the authorities. It would have been impossible to maintain standards of hygiene, the general level of morbidity would have been raised, and there would have been an exaltation of pathogenic virulence. In traditional societies, it is

usually the first-born who are given the opportunity to avail themselves of privilege when a choice must be made due to limited family resources. In the circumstances imagined here therefore, they would have taken the brunt of the last plague.

Even if we concede that this chain of events is possible, however improbable, there still remains a serious obstacle. Why is it that only the Egyptians suffered from the plagues, whilst the Hebrews living amongst them were apparently immune? Perhaps if we are prepared to stretch credibility a little further, we can answer this question too. The first chapter of Exodus (Ex. 1: 7), tells us that “the children of Israel were fruitful, and increased abundantly, and multiplied, and waxed exceeding mighty; and the land was filled with them.” and (Ex. 1: 12) “the more they (Egyptians) afflicted them, the more they multiplied and grew”. The pharaoh tried to institute a number of measures, including infanticide, to curb their fer-

tility, but these were unsuccessful. The Israelis were clearly *r*-strategists. Migration is characteristic of *r*-strategists in deteriorating habitats. Hence by labelling the Israelis *r*-strategists, we can account both for their survival in a rapidly changing environment, and for the *Exodus* itself.

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IOC Training Course

IOC Training Course and Identification Qualification in Harmful Marine Microalgae, August-October 2023

The purpose of the course, organized by the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen, Denmark Copenhagen, Denmark, is to improve the taxonomic and identification skills of the participants for research purposes and for practical monitoring of harmful algal blooms. The course also includes a practical exam at the end of Part 2, with an IOC Certificate of Proficiency in Identification of Harmful Algae issued to participants who pass the exam..

The course, aimed at participants who have some years of practical experience in identification of microalgae includes 100 hours of teaching and is divided into two parts:

1. The first part of the course is an internet teaching programme on the Ocean Teacher platform giving general introductions to the various groups of harmful algae; this part is mainly for self-study and estimated to 40 hours of reading. Part 1 will be available on the ‘International Oceanographic Data Exchange’ (IODE) teaching platform ‘Ocean Teacher’ from August onwards;
2. The second part is a practical course in species identification including 60 hours of teaching. A microscope will be available to each participant during the entire period. Part 2 takes place from 15-26 October 2023

Participants

The course is aimed at participants who have some years of practical experience in identification of microalgae.

The number of participants is limited to 16. If there are more applicants than available seats, priority will be given to applicants who have direct research or management responsibilities with regard to the occurrence of harmful algae.

Venue (Part 2)

IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen, Denmark, c/o Danhostel, Lejrskolevej 4, 3400 Hillerød.

Application

Deadline for application is **1 June 2023**

Details on the programme, teacher, and practical information can be found the [IOC-HAB website](#)

Enquiries may be sent to Jacob Larsen, jacobl@bio.ku.dk

Forthcoming

International Workshop on Solutions to Control HABs in Marine and Estuarine Waters

The **International Workshop on Solutions to Control HABs in Marine and Estuarine Waters** is scheduled for October 21 and 22, 2023.

The workshop is sponsored by the Global Harmful Algal Blooms (*Global-HAB*) Programme and the North Pacific Marine Science Organization (*PICES*) and will be held in conjunction with the PICES Annual meeting in Seattle, Washington, USA.

The workshop will specifically focus on HAB control methods that affect the target HAB organisms themselves, either killing them or removing cells and/or toxins from the water. There will also be a strong focus on methods that have been field tested. However, some advanced lab methods may be

considered if strong evidence is provided about their suitability for use in the field. Lessons will be drawn from experiences in freshwater HAB control. Discussions will include effectiveness for use in marine systems, cost, scalability, regulatory hurdles issues and approaches for communicating with the public and stakeholders. The workshop will not focus on bloom prevention or HAB mitigation efforts to relieve the impact of blooms, such as monitoring and forecasting.

This workshop will be held in person with no opportunity for remote or absentee participation. Presentations are by invitation only and an associated poster session is planned. The venue is the Westin Seattle Hotel. Registration will be handled via the PICES-2023 Annual Meeting [website](#). A user logon (pre-registration) must be established on the PICES website as a first step, at

[this link](#). Workshop attendees must register for the full meeting with a cost of \$250 Canadian dollars (CAD) before June 15. After June 15, the registration cost will increase to \$350 CAD. Students and invited speakers are offered a reduced registration cost of \$50 CAD. Abstract submissions will be accepted online [here](#) until June 15 2023 with acceptance notifications coming about a month later. Financial support applications can be submitted [here](#) through June 15. (See [abstract](#) for affiliations and more details).

The organizing committee hopes to see you there!

Vera Trainer, Quay Dortch, Marc Suddleson, Pengbin Wang, Mark Wells, Natsuko Nakayama, Don Anderson, Heather Raymond, Hae Jin Jeong, H. Dail Laughinghouse

The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae invites you to the **20th biennial International Conference on Harmful Algae** on November 5-10, 2023, at the Grand Prince Hotel Hiroshima in Hiroshima, Japan. The [conference website](#) is open for registration with abstract submission through 19th June 2023! Sign-ups for the banquet and excursions will be announced in April. Please note there are several conferences using the same name as ours (ICHA 2023) but these have absolutely no relationship with our official conference website (<https://icha2023.org>).

We aim to provide a safe in-person event for scientists, policymakers, and practitioners to share their knowledge and gather ideas regarding all aspects of marine and freshwater harmful algae. Limited online participation will be possible as well.

This conference provides a unique forum for collaboration, connection and sharing ideas. We hope that you will join us for this opportunity to connect with the global harmful algae community.

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Book announcement

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 73:
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